

and 630 nm. The high energy band at 260 nm is due to the intraligand transition³. The band around 490 nm is assigned⁴ to (S)→d (Cr) charge transfer rather than O(π)→d (Cr) transition. A similar, (S)→d (Mo) charge transfer transition is present in molybdenum complexes⁵. The low energy band observed around 630 nm for chromium complexes is probably due to the d→d transition⁶.

The ir spectra of the complexes exhibit (Table 1) a strong band in the range 990–1 020 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of Cr=O stretching⁷. The ν_{C-N} band of dithiocarbamic acid occurs in the region 1 542–1 480 cm⁻¹⁸. Hence the band at ~1 480 cm⁻¹ is assigned to the polar C=N group⁹. The ν_{σ-S} occurs around 960 cm⁻¹ due to the univalent bidentate ligand¹⁰ and ν_{σr-s} and ν_{σr-σi} of the complexes appear at 510 and 360 cm⁻¹, respectively¹¹.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the authorities of Madras Christian College, Madras, for facilities.

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Trigonal Complexes of Mercuric Cyanide and Thiocyanide with p-Nitrobenzoylhydrazine

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Manuscript received 7 May 1985, revised 24 February 1988,
accepted 17 March 1988

p-Nitrobenzoylhydrazine (PNBH) has been reported^{1,2} to react with metal ions in different ways, N-donor and/or O-donor depending on the reaction conditions. Mercury(II) is also known to form complexes in which it can have a variety of coordination numbers ranging from two to six^{3,4}, but three is very rare. The present paper reports

the formation of two three-coordinate mercury(II) complexes of the title ligand.

Experimental

The ligand was prepared according to the reported procedure⁵ from hydrazine hydrate and p-nitroethylbenzoate. The complexes [Hg(PNBH)₂X₂] (X=CN or SCN) were prepared by the slow addition with continuous stirring of an ethanolic solution of the ligand to a hot ethanolic solution of mercury(II) salt in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The mixture on heating (30 min) at 50–60° and subsequent cooling gave a pale yellow compound which was filtered, washed with ethanol and dried, (Found (Calcd.) : for X=CN, C, 25.06 (24.94); H, 1.68 (1.62); N, 16.28 (16.17); Hg, 46.22 (46.19); and for X=SCN, C, 21.65 (21.63); H, 1.45 (1.41); N, 14.19 (14.08); Hg, 40.36 (40.25).

Conductivity measurements of complexes were carried out at 25° on freshly prepared 10⁻³ M solutions in acetonitrile using MC-1 conductivity bridge. The infrared absorption spectra (nujol, KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 spectrophotometer (200–4 000 cm⁻¹).

Results and Discussion

Both the complexes which are insoluble in most of the organic solvents are slightly soluble in acetonitrile and behave as non-electrolytes (Λ, 22–25 S cm⁻¹ mol⁻¹). Their ir spectra reveal ν_{σ-O} bands at almost the same frequencies as that of the free ligand (1 650 cm⁻¹). However, lowering of the δ_{NH} of NH₂ group of the ligand from 1 615 cm⁻¹ by 25 cm⁻¹ suggests the coordination of the ligand through NH₂ nitrogen only¹. The lowering of ν_{σ-N} (2 193 cm⁻¹), ν_{Hσ-O} (442 cm⁻¹) and δ_{Hg-CN} (341 cm⁻¹) of Hg(CN)₂ bands by 20–30 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of [Hg(PNBH)(CN)₂] indicate the presence of terminal CN groups^{8–12}. The appearance of ν_{C-N}, ν_{σ-S} and δ_{σ-S} bands at 2 115, 715, and 450 and 420 cm⁻¹, respectively, in the spectrum of [Hg(PNBH)(SCN)₂] also favours the terminal coordination of NCS to mercury(II) through sulphur^{12–14}. In view of the monodentate action of PNBH and terminal coordination of CN and NCS both the complexes may be assigned monomeric neutral three-coordinate structure in the solid state.

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*Above 60° grey mixtures of Hg²⁺ and Hg^I were formed. Due to formation of such mixture, attempts to prepare other Hg²⁺ salt with PNBH were unsuccessful.

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Photochemical Reduction of Ferric Oxalate in a Solid pressed Potassium Bromide Disk

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*Manuscript received 6 June 1986, revised 19 October 1987,
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IN continuation of our work on the photochemical reaction in solid pressed potassium bromide disk^{1,2}, we have studied the photochemical reaction of ferric oxalate.

Experimental

The transparent potassium bromide disks were prepared by mixing ferric oxalate (1 mg) with KBr (1 g) in a vibrator and the mixture was pressed under vacuum into disk (250 mg; 14.5 mm dia × 1.0 mm). The disk was irradiated with ultraviolet light from a Phillips 125 W uv lamp for 1 and 2 h and infrared spectra were recorded after each irradiation on a Perkin-Elmer 377 grating spectrophotometer, to follow the course of photochemical reactions.

Results and Discussion

The reaction products were identified by characterising the ir spectra of ferric oxalate before and after the irradiation and by chemical means. The results were also compared with the ir spectra of the disk acting as control by keeping the disk in dark and taking their spectra after 0, 1 and 2 h. No change in the position of the bands were observed, which indicates that no reaction has taken place in the dark.

The comparison of spectra before and after irradiation revealed shift of the position of several bands, and some of the bands disappeared and some new bands appeared. Gradual appearance of a

band at 2 350–2 330 cm⁻¹ was assigned to the formation of carbon dioxide³. It is observed that a broad band centered at 1 670 cm⁻¹ shifted to 1 635 cm⁻¹ (C=O)⁴. A broad band at 1 430 cm⁻¹ gradually disappeared and lost after 2 h of irradiation. The bands at 1 345 and 1 270 cm⁻¹ shifting to 1 360 and 1 315 cm⁻¹ were attributed to the $\nu_{\sigma-O} + \nu_{\sigma-\sigma}$ and $\nu_{\sigma-O} + \delta_{O-\sigma-O}$, respectively. The intensity of the band at 870 cm⁻¹ increased after irradiation which was assigned to $\nu_{\sigma-O} + \delta_{O-C-O}$ band. In the same way, the band at 805 cm⁻¹ shifting to 820 cm⁻¹ was attributed to $\delta_{O-\sigma-O} + \delta_{M-O}$. A new band appeared after irradiation at 665 cm⁻¹, and shifting of the band at 490 from 530 cm⁻¹ with the increase in band intensity was attributed to $\nu_{M-O} + \nu_{O-\sigma}$.

Thus the appearance, disappearance and shifts in the position of bands revealed the reduction of ferric oxalate into ferrous oxalate with the formation of carbon dioxide. The formation of ferrous oxalate is further confirmed by dissolving the ferric oxalate pellet before and after irradiation in the dilute solution of potassium permanganate. The permanganate solution containing irradiated pellet decolourised slowly compared to the solution containing non-irradiated pellet, inferring that ferric oxalate is reduced to ferrous oxalate according to the following stoichiometric relationship,

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Kinetics of Oxidation of Thiocyanate Ion by Dichloramine-B in Partially Aqueous Medium

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*Manuscript received 16 July 1987, revised 18 April 1988,
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THE chemistry of *N*-halogeno-*N*-metalloaromatic sulphonamides is of interest due to their diverse behaviour. They are sources of halonium cations and hypohalite species¹. Dichloramine-B (DCB) in an important member of the benzene analogue

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